

A study to assess the knowledge regarding benefits of wheat grass juice among nursing students at selected nursing college, rajnandgaon (C.G.)

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Abstract:

Wheat grass juice is often called 'Green Blood' because of its rich chlorophyll content, which closely resembles human hemoglobin in structure and function. Chlorophyll helps in oxygen transportation, blood purification, and boosting overall vitality. It contains more than 100 nutrients, including vitamins A, C, E, K, and B-complex, minerals such as calcium, magnesium, potassium, and iron, and 17 amino acids, 8 of which are essential for human health. It is especially beneficial in conditions like anemia, thalassemia, liver disorders, diabetes, and digestive problems. A pre-experimental one-group pre-test post-test design. Convenient sampling technique was considered to be appropriate sampling technique to select the 200 B.Sc. nursing students of IInd, IVth, VIth and VIIth semesters at Govt. College of Nursing Rajnandgaon (C.G.). After implementing structured teaching program - video cum demonstration and distribution of pamphlet regarding benefits of wheat grass juice. The post-test knowledge score of study subject of majority 123 (61.5%) were having excellent knowledge and 75(37.5%) were having very good knowledge and the comparison between pre-test and post-test score on knowledge regarding benefits of wheat grass juice among Bachelor of Science in Nursing students. There was statistically significant increase in the knowledge of study subjects shows that $t(199) = 30.316$ more than table value (1.646), at 0.05 significant level. Beside that there was statistically significant association between pre-test knowledge score with educational status of mother ($p < 0.05$) shows that students with mother studied till secondary classes scored more compare to students having illiterate mother due to the fact that they have better health literacy and greater access to reliable health information. There was a statistically significant increase in the knowledge of study subjects following the structured teaching programme and pamphlet distribution regarding benefits of wheat grass juice. There was a statistically significant association between pre-test knowledge score with educational status of mother.
